

PROPERTIES OF (i, j) SEMI-BITOLOGICAL GROUPS

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Abstract:

In this paper, we introduce and study a class of bitopologized groups called (i, j) - semi-bitopological groups.

1. Introduction:

If $(G, *)$ is a group, and τ_1 and τ_2 are topologies on G , then we say that $(G, *, \tau_1, \tau_2)$ is a bitopologized group. Given a bitopologized group G , a question arises about interactions and relations between algebraic and bitopological structures: which topological properties are satisfied by the multiplication mapping $m : G \times G \rightarrow G, (x, y) \rightarrow x * y$, and the inverse mapping $i : G \rightarrow G, x \rightarrow x^{-1}$. In this paper, we introduce and study a class of bitopologized groups called (i, j)-semi-bitopological groups.

2. Preliminaries:

Throughout this paper $(G, *, \tau_1, \tau_2)$, or simply G , will denote a group $(G, *)$ endowed with the topologies τ_1 and τ_2 on G . The identity element of G is denoted by e , or e_G when it is necessary, the operation $* : G \times G \rightarrow G, (x, y) \rightarrow x * y$, is called the multiplication mapping and sometimes denoted by m , and the inverse mapping $i : G \rightarrow G, x \rightarrow x^{-1}$ is denoted by i . For a subset A of a topological space (X, τ_i) , $i Cl(A)$ and $i Int(A)$ denote the closure of A and interior of A in (X, τ_i) , respectively.

Definition 2.1: [2] A subset S of a bitopological space (X, τ_1, τ_2) is said to be (i, j)-semiopen if $S \subset j Cl(i Int(S))$. The complement of an (i, j)-semiopen set is called an (i, j)-semiclosed set.

Definition 2.2: [2] The intersection of all (i, j)-semiclosed sets containing $S \subset X$ is called (i, j)-semiclosure of S and is denoted by $(i, j)\text{-}s Cl(S)$. The family of all (i, j)-semiopen (resp. (i, j)-semiclosed) sets of (X, τ_1, τ_2) is denoted by $(i, j)\text{-}SO(X)$ (resp. $(i, j)\text{-}SC(X)$). The family of all (i, j)-semiopen (resp. (i, j)-semiclosed) sets of (X, τ_1, τ_2) containing a point $x \in X$ is denoted by $(i, j)\text{-}SO(X, x)$ (resp. $(i, j)\text{-}SC(X, x)$).

Definition 2.3: A function $f : (X, \tau_1, \tau_2) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_1, \sigma_2)$ is said to be :

- (1) (i, j)-semicontinuous [2] if $f^{-1}(V) \in (i, j)\text{-}SO(X)$ for every $V \in \sigma_i$.
- (2) (i, j)-irresolute [1] if $f^{-1}(V) \in (i, j)\text{-}SO(X)$ for every $V \in (i, j)\text{-}SO(Y)$.
- (3) Pre-irresolute if $f(V) \in (i, j)\text{-}SO(Y)$ for every $V \in (i, j)\text{-}SO(X)$.
- (4) (i, j)-semihomomorphism if f is bijective, (i, j)-irresolute and pre-(i, j)-semiopen.

Lemma 2.4: If $f : (X, \tau_1, \tau_2) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_1, \sigma_2)$ is an (i, j)-semihomomorphism then:

- (1) $(i, j)\text{-}s Cl(f(A)) = f((i, j)\text{-}s Cl(A))$ for all $A \subset X$;
- (2) $(i, j)\text{-}s Int(f(A)) = f((i, j)\text{-}s Int(A))$ for all $A \subset X$.

Definition 2.5: A subset U of (X, τ_1, τ_2) is called an (i, j)-semineighbourhood of a point $x \in X$ if there exists an (i, j)-semiopen set V of (X, τ_1, τ_2) such that $x \in V \subset U$.

3. Quasi Topological Groups:

Definition 3.1: (G, o, τ_1, τ_2) is (i, j)-semi-bitopological group if (G, o) is a group, (G, τ_1, τ_2) is a bitopological space and left translation $L_x : G \rightarrow G$ for all $x \in G$ and right translation $R_x : G \rightarrow G$ for all $x \in G$ are (i, j)-semicontinuous and the mapping of inversion $i : G \rightarrow G$ defined by $i(x) = x^{-1}$ is (i, j)-semicontinuous on G .

Theorem 3.2:

Let (G, o, τ_1, τ_2) be an (i, j)-semi-bitopological group and β_e be the base at identity element e of G .

Then:

- (1) For every $U \in \beta_e$, there is an element $V \in (i, j)\text{-}SO(G, e)$ such that $V^{-1} \subset U$.
- (2) For every $U \in \beta_e$, there is an element V such that $x \in V$ and $x \circ V \subset U$ for each $x \in U$.

Proof:

(1) Since (G, o, τ_1, τ_2) is an (i, j)-semi-bitopological group. Therefore, for every $U \in \beta_e$ there exists $V \in (i, j)\text{-}SO(G, e)$ such that $i(V) = V^{-1} \in U$ because the inverse mapping $i : G \rightarrow G$ is (i, j)-semicontinuous.

(2) Since (G, o, τ_1, τ_2) is an (i, j)-semi-bitopological group. Thus, for each $U \in \tau_i$ containing x , there exists $V \in (i, j)\text{-}SO(G, e)$ such that $R_x(V) = V \circ x \subset U$.

Lemma 3.3:

Let A be a subset of an (i, j)-semi-bitopological group (G, o, τ, σ) . Then $(i, j)\text{-}s Cl(A^{-1}) \in i Cl(A^{-1})$.

Proof:

Let $x \in ((i, j)\text{-}s\ Cl(A))^{-1}$ and let $U \in \tau_i$ containing x . Then, U^{-1} is an (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhood of x^{-1} . Since $x^{-1} \in (i, j)\text{-}s\ Cl(A)$, therefore, $U^{-1} \cap A \neq \emptyset$. This implies that $U \cap A^{-1} \neq \emptyset$. That is, $x \in i\ Cl(A^{-1})$ and so $((i, j)\text{-}s\ Cl(A))^{-1} \subset i\ Cl(A^{-1})$.

Remark 3.4: If (G, o, τ_1, τ_2) is a quasi bitopological group, then τ_i^{-1} is also a topology on G , called conjugate topology of τ_i . If (G, o, τ_1, τ_2) is a quasi bitopological group, then so is $(G, o, \tau_1^{-1}, \tau_2^{-1})$. Note that $\tau_i^{-1} = \{A \subset G : A^{-1} \in \tau_i\}$. We give the following important result:

Theorem 3.5:

Let (G, o, τ_1, τ_2) be an (i, j) -semi-bitopological group. If U is (i, j) -semiopen set in (G, o, τ_1, τ_2) , then U^{-1} is (i, j) -semiopen in $(G, o, \tau_1^{-1}, \tau_2^{-1})$.

Proof:

The proof follows from the respective definitions.

Theorem 3.6:

If (G, o, τ_1, τ_2) is (i, j) -semi-bitopological group, then $(G, o, \tau_1^{-1}, \tau_2^{-1})$ is also an (i, j) -semi-bitopological group.

Proof:

Since (G, o) is a group, (G, τ_1, τ_2) is a bitopological space. Therefore, $(G, o, \tau_1^{-1}, \tau_2^{-1})$ is again a bitopological group. We need to prove that: $i = (G, o, \tau_1^{-1}, \tau_2^{-1}) \rightarrow (G, o, \tau_1, \tau_2)$, and $L_x : (G, o, \tau_1^{-1}, \tau_2^{-1}) \rightarrow (G, o, \tau_1, \tau_2)$ and $R_x : (G, \tau_1^{-1}) \rightarrow (G, \tau_1)$ are (i, j) -semicontinuous mappings. First, we show that L_x is (i, j) -semicontinuous. For this, let $V \in \tau_i^{-1}$. Then $V^{-1} = U \in \tau_i$. Since (G, o, τ_1, τ_2) is (i, j) -semi-bitopological group, the left (right) translation is (i, j) -semicontinuous. Hence $L_x^{-1}(U) \in (i, j)\text{-}SO(G, \tau_1, \tau_2)$, that is, $(U \circ x^{-1})^{-1} \in (i, j)\text{-}SO(G, \tau_1^{-1}, \tau_2^{-1})$, that is, $U \circ x^{-1} = V^{-1} \circ x^{-1} = (x \circ v)^{-1} = L_x^{-1}(V) \in (i, j)\text{-}SO(G, \tau_1^{-1}, \tau_2^{-1})$. This proves that $L_x : (G, o, \tau_1^{-1}, \tau_2^{-1}) \rightarrow (G, o, \tau_1, \tau_2)$ is (i, j) -semicontinuous for every $x \in G$. Similarly, we can prove that right translation $R_x : (G, o, \tau_1^{-1}, \tau_2^{-1}) \rightarrow (G, o, \tau_1, \tau_2)$ is (i, j) -semicontinuous. Trivially $i : (G, o, \tau_1^{-1}, \tau_2^{-1}) \rightarrow (G, o, \tau_1, \tau_2)$ is continuous and hence (i, j) -semicontinuous. Hence $(G, o, \tau_1^{-1}, \tau_2^{-1})$ is also an (i, j) -semi-bitopological group.

Theorem 3.7:

If H is a discrete subgroup of an (i, j) -semi-bitopological group $(G, o, \tau_1^{-1}, \tau_2^{-1})$, then $(i, j)\text{-}s\ Cl(H)$ is a subgroup of G .

Proof:

Let $x, y \in (i, j)\text{-}s\ Cl(H)$. If U and V are respective open neighbourhoods of x and y , then $L_x^{-1}(U) = x^{-1} \circ U$ and $L_y^{-1}(U) = y^{-1} \circ U$ are (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhood of e . Since H is a discrete subgroup of an (i, j) -semi-bitopological group G , therefore, $x^{-1} \circ U \cap H \neq \emptyset$ and $y^{-1} \circ U \cap H \neq \emptyset$. Therefore, $(x \circ y^{-1} \circ x^{-1} \circ U \cap x \circ y^{-1} \circ H) \cup (x \circ y^{-1} \circ y^{-1} \circ V \cap x \circ y^{-1} \circ H) \neq \emptyset$. That is $W \cap x^{-1} \circ y^{-1} \circ H \neq \emptyset$, where $W = x \circ y^{-1} \circ x^{-1} \circ U \cup x \circ y^{-1} \circ y^{-1} \circ V$ is an (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhood of $x \circ y^{-1}$. Thus, for each $x, y \in (i, j)\text{-}s\ Cl(H)$ implies that $x \circ y^{-1} \in (i, j)\text{-}s\ Cl(H)$. Hence $(i, j)\text{-}s\ Cl(H)$ is a subgroup of G .

Corollary 3.8:

If H is a discrete subgroup of an (i, j) -semibitopological group (G, o, τ_1, τ_2) then $i\ Cl(H)$ is a subgroup of G .

Theorem 3.9:

Let (G, o, τ_1, τ_2) be an (i, j) -semi-bitopological group. If A is open in G , then $A \circ B$ and $B \circ A$ are (i, j) -semiopen in (G, o, τ_1, τ_2) for any subset B of G .

Proof:

Let $x \in B$ and $Z \in A \circ x$ we show that z is (i, j) -semiinterior point of $A \circ x$, Let $z = y \circ x$ for some $y \in A = A \circ x \circ x^{-1}$. This implies that $y = z \circ x^{-1}$. Now $R_{x^{-1}} : G \rightarrow G$ is (i, j) -semicontinuous, that is, for every open set containing $R_{x^{-1}}(z) = z \circ x^{-1} = y$, there exists an (i, j) -semiopen set M_z containing z such that $R_{x^{-1}}(M_z) \subset A$. This implies $M_z \circ x^{-1} \subset A$ or $M_z \subset A \circ x$. This implies z is (i, j) -semiinterior point of $A \circ x$. Thus $A \circ x$ is (i, j) -semiopen. This implies $A \circ B = \cup_{x \in B} A \circ x$ is (i, j) -semiopen in (G, o, τ_1, τ_2) . Similarly we can prove that for every open set A of G and arbitrary subset B of G , $B \circ A$ is (i, j) -semiopen in an (i, j) -semi-bitopological group (G, o, τ_1, τ_2) .

Definition 3.10: A bijective mapping $f : (X, \tau_X, \mathcal{G}) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_Y, \mathcal{H})$ is called quasi $s\text{-}\mathcal{G}$ -homeomorphism if it is (i, j) -semicontinuous and (i, j) -semiopen.

Theorem 3.11:

Let (G, o, τ_1, τ_2) be an (i, j) -semi-bitopological group. Then each left (right) translation $L_x : G \rightarrow G$ is $R_x : G \rightarrow G$ a quasi $s\text{-}\mathcal{G}$ -homeomorphism.

Proof:

Since (G, o, τ_1, τ_2) is (i, j) -semi-bitopological group. Therefore, $L_x : G \rightarrow G$ is (i, j) -semicontinuous. So it is enough to show that $L_x : G \rightarrow G$ is (i, j) -semiopen. Let V be an open set in G . Then by Theorem 3.9, $L_x(V) = g \circ V \in SO(G)$. Hence $L_x : G \rightarrow G$ is an (i, j) -semiopen mapping.

Theorem 3.12:

Suppose that a subgroup H of an (i, j) -semi-bitopological group (G, o, τ_1, τ_2) contains a nonempty open subset of G . Then H is semiopen in G .

Proof:

By Theorem 3.11 for every $g \in H$, $R_g: G \rightarrow G$ is quasi s -homeomorphism. Let U be a nonempty open subset of G with $U \subset H$, then for every $g \in H$, the set $R_g(U) = U \circ g$ is (i, j) -semiopen in (G, o, τ_1, τ_2) . Now $H = U \cup \{U \circ g : g \in H\}$ is (i, j) -semiopen in G being union of (i, j) -semiopen sets of G .

Definition 3.13: A topological space (G, τ) is said to be quasi s -homogeneous if for all $x, y \in G$, there is a quasi s -homomorphism f of the space G onto itself such that $f(x) = y$.

Theorem 3.14:

If (G, o, τ_1, τ_2) is an (i, j) -semi-bitopological group, then every open subgroup of G is also (i, j) -semiclosed.

Proof:

Since (G, o, τ_1, τ_2) is an (i, j) -semi-bitopological group and H is an open subgroup of G . Then any left or right translation $x \circ H$ or $H \circ x$ is (i, j) -semiopen for each $x \in G$. So $Y = \{x \circ H : x \in G\}$ of all left cosets of H in G forms a partition of G . Thus Y is an (i, j) -semiopen covering of G . by disjoint (i, j) -semiopen sets of G . This gives $G \setminus H$ is union of (i, j) -semiopen sets and hence (i, j) -semiopen. This proves that H is (i, j) -semiclosed.

Corollary 3.15:

Every (i, j) -semi-bitopological group is a quasi s -homogeneous space.

Proof:

Let us take element x and y in (G, o, τ_1, τ_2) , and put $z = x^{-1} \circ y$. Since $R_x: G \rightarrow G$ is a quasi s -homeomorphism of (G, o, τ_1, τ_2) and $R_z(x) = x \circ z = x \circ (x^{-1} \circ y) = e \circ y = y$. Hence (G, o, τ_1, τ_2) is quasi s -homogeneous space.

Lemma 3.16: If $f: (X, \tau_X) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_Y)$ is (i, j) -semicontinuous and H is open subset of X , then $f_H: (H, \tau_H) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_Y)$ is (i, j) -semicontinuous.

Theorem 3.17:

Every open subgroup H of an (i, j) -semi-bitopological group (G, o, τ_1, τ_2) is also an (i, j) -semi-bitopological group (called (i, j) -semi-bitopological subgroup) of G .

Proof:

Let (G, o, τ_1, τ_2) be an (i, j) -semi-bitopological group and H be an open subgroup of G . We need to prove that (H, o, τ_H) is an (i, j) -semi-bitopological group. For this, We show that $i: H \rightarrow H$, $L_x: H \rightarrow H$ and $R_x: H \rightarrow H$ are (i, j) -semicontinuous with respect to the relative topology. Since H is an open subgroup of G . Then by Lemma 3.16, $i_H: (H, \tau_H) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_Y)$, $L_H: (H, \tau_H) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_Y)$ and $R_H: (H, \tau_H) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_Y)$ are (i, j) -semicontinuous. This proves that (H, o, τ_H) is an (i, j) -semi-bitopological group.

Theorem 3.18:

Let $f: (G, o, \tau_G) \rightarrow (H, o, \tau_H)$ be a homomorphism of (i, j) -semi-bitopological groups. If f is (i, j) -irresolute at the natural (identity) element e_G , then f is (i, j) -semicontinuous on G .

Proof:

Let $x \in G$ be an arbitrary element. Suppose that W is an open neighbourhood of $y = f(x) \in H$. Since the left translation in H is an (i, j) -semicontinuous mapping, there is an (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhood V of the neutral element e_H of H such that $L_y(V) = y \circ V \subset W$. Since f is (i, j) -irresolute at e_G , therefore, $f(U) \subset V$ for some (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhood U of e_G in G . Since $f(U) \subset V$, now $y \circ f(U) \subset y \circ V \subset W$. This implies $(x \circ U) \subset W$. Since (G, o, τ_G) is an (i, j) -semi-bitopological group, $x \circ U$ is (i, j) -semiopen in G . This proves that f is (i, j) -semicontinuous at x . Since x was the arbitrary element of G , f is (i, j) -semicontinuous on G .

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